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Novel challenges for root cause investigation in semiconductor manufacturing

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This project has received funding from the ECSEL Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 783163. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and Austria (BMVIT-IKT der Zukunft, FFG project no. 865348), Germany, Belgium, Italy, Spain, Romania.

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Motivation

Due to the constantly growing automation in the semiconductor manufacturing and the associated increasing amount of data, the question of data handling and automated decision making becomes more and more important. Advanced measurement techniques in high-precision and high-tech manufacturing processes lead to more data and hence, enable more monitoring possibilities. Nevertheless, recorded data is only meaningful if evaluated. Common root cause analyses, performed by experts, are mainly based on physical relations and lower order correlations aiming to keep the manufacturing process stable. To investigate higher order correlations, especially if there is an increased data landscape available, needs automated evaluation procedures because manual effort is not feasible anymore. Therefore, novel investigation procedures are needed by means of data- and knowledge-driven analysis methods to support the expert's routine in order to perform root cause analysis.

Description

In Frontend production, the semiconductor devices are assembled and manufactured in hundreds of successive process steps on so-called wafers. After Frontend production, all components on the wafer are thoroughly tested to meet the requirements of the respective application areas. This wafer testing allows to check whether certain test variables such as voltage, current, resistance, etc. of the devices are within predefined specification limits, summarized as so-called wafer test data. In order to visualize these data, so-called wafermaps are used (cf. Figure 1 right) which occasionally show product critical patterns, where its root cause is searched for in the Frontend production to e.g. apply possible countermeasures. The current procedure of root cause analysis leads to time-consuming and in the meantime costly proceedings performed by experts. Our aim is to develop a faster and more targeted root cause investigation procedure by using data-driven machine learning methods, enriched with expert knowledge. For this purpose, a large number of production data is available. We focus on equipment data (APC - Advanced Process Control / FDC - Fault Detection & Classification) such as pressure, temperature, gas flows, etc., which is recorded by the equipment during the respective process step. The recording takes place at regular time steps and results in so-called trace data (cf. Figure 1 left). Out of the trace data, so-called key numbers are extracted (cf. Figure 1 center). The resulting numbers are statistical values like mean, standard deviation, maximum, minimum, etc., with the quantity of key numbers varying for one trace depending on the judgment of the expert responsible for the equipment and the process.

The goal is to find correlations between APC/FDC data (trace data or key numbers) and patterns in wafer test data using machine learning methods to determine the root cause of interesting patterns in the wafer test data.

Innovation

Due to the ever increasing amount of data in semiconductor device manufacturing, it is getting more and more difficult for experts to continuously monitor the large number of measurements. The data-driven root cause analysis is intended to act as a supporting tool

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for the current time-intensive procedures of experts, who are then able to take faster and more targeted countermeasures by combining knowledge of the semiconductor manufacturing with statistical data science. Combining measurement data from several types of production equipment leads to deeper insight into previously unknown coherences. With the incorporation of data-driven methods for root cause analysis, not only analysis time can be saved, but also production costs.

Results

The approach of using data-driven machine learning methods conceals some challenges. Due to the arbitrarily large quantity of APC/FDC data and the high number of measurements performed at wafer testing, the resulting data set is very large. To handle this, a suitable dimension reduction procedure, which extracts the most important features (information) out of the data is necessary. To do so, there is a wide range of possible methods, whereas Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is one of the most common procedures.

However, if there are missing values caused by different reasons like general availability, recording difficulties and defects as well as calibration errors, applying PCA is not possible anymore. Alternatively, Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) can be applied, which can handle missing values.

Since the number of influencing variables is high and the correlations are very complex, highly sophisticated methods must be applied which additionally can handle the occurring big data challenges, including efficient software solutions with sufficient possibilities for data exchange and data handling.

Furthermore, different data sources exhibit heterogeneous data quality and granularity. For instance, APC key numbers are given at wafer level, i.e. one measurement per wafer, but wafer test data are recorded at device level, i.e. one measurement per device on the wafer (cf. Figure 1). Therefore, the automated matching of different data sources and granularities appears as a crucial part in order to keep important information. To handle this issue, we introduce the method of Multilevel Modeling in the context of root cause analysis. This approach allows us to exploit different data granularities and data qualities instead of simply aggregating information, which contains the risk of losing valuable information. It is a "level-based" procedure (cf. Figure 2), which makes it possible to correlate different types of equipment, even with a varying number of chambers.

Due to the fact that there are hundreds of equipment types in fabrication that can influence the variation in the wafer test data individually or in combination, it is of essential importance to incorporate experiences and guidance from experts. Without this semantic information, the danger of numerous false alarms caused by huge amounts of predictive variables in the data will be unacceptably high. One possible way to integrate expert knowledge into root cause analysis is to apply Bayesian approaches. By combining a-priori (expert) knowledge with the given data, it becomes possible to strengthen or even exclude certain correlations in

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advance. This approach acts like a pre-processing step before data-driven analysis is performed in order to evaluate only reasonable interrelations.

Figure 1: The analog wafer test data (right) show an interesting pattern, which has to be linked to APC key numbers (center) calculated out of their corresponding APC trace data (left).

Figure 2: Example for a 3-step Multilevel Model in order to handle different data granularities.